

Title: Examine ICO

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INTRODUCTION:

One of blockchain applications is ICO. This has quickly become a trend that will change the future of finance

AIM:

To give a description of the landscape of ICO globally.

RESULTS:

There are more money raised with ICO than with VC at the same period this year.

CONCLUSIONS:

The killer application on Blockchain is ICO and by tokenize everything, we are quickly going to the future into the digital economy.

BIOGRAPHY:

Jane Zhang, the founder and CEO of the Pioneer of blockchain company Shellpay .

Jane Zhang is a famous angel investor and entrepreneur from Shanghai. She was an early investor of Alibaba, UT Starcom and VIPS(NYSE listed company), graduated from Georgetown University and Harvard MBA. She used to work in McKinsey, is strong at strategy planning.

Shellpay has been selected by DFA for their 2017 Spring program, they are now working with Immigration office to develop Blockchain solutions